

Tuning the morphology and structure of vertical graphene nanowalls: Raman and EELS study

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Abstract

The influence of process gas composition on the morphology and structure of vertical graphene nanowalls (VGNs) deposited by plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) is studied. Argon percentage was systemically varied against methane under similar process conditions. Both morphological and structural variations were revealed from SEM and Raman studies. The crystallite size calculated from ID/IG ratio showed a direct correlation with increase in methane concentration. The ID/ID' ratio was correlated with gas mixture to infer the characteristics of defects in VGNs. In concurrence with SEM and Raman study, 'a few layer graphene' structure was revealed from TEM analysis. Selected area diffraction pattern showed nanocrystalline nature of VGNs and decrease in d-spacing with increase in methane concentration. In the low loss region of electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), σ^* plasmon showed a minimum at 1:1 gas ratio, whereas π^* Plasmon became more graphitic with increase in methane concentration. A lower fraction of sp² type bonding was observed for 1:1 concentration in the high loss region[1]. The present study showed that inert Argon can be effectively used for tuning the plasmonic properties of VGNs towards better super capacitor, field emission, catalytic and fuel cell applications.

1. G-normalised Raman spectra showing variation of D-band int. with composition

2. π^* normalised EELS spectra of VGNs and HOPG for sp² percentage calculation

3. HR TEM image showing the few layer VGNs

Key words: PECVD, VGNs, Raman spectroscopy, EELS

[1] Bernier N et al. Jnl of Electron Spectroscopy and Related Phenomena. 2008;164(1):34